

TYPES OF REHABILITATION

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Abstract. Rehabilitation is a process aimed at restoring a person's ability to function in a social environment, as a technology, it promotes a set of measures aimed at rehabilitation at the medical, household, professional, and personal levels. It is a type of activity aimed at the social adjustment of the child in society, restoration of his social status, restoration of lost relationships, and includes a set of measures aimed at restoring the ability of a person to function in a social environment.

Key words: Rehabilitation, organism, nervous system, pneumonia, recovery, physiotherapy, hypertension, physical activity, mental recovery.

ВИДЫ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ

Аннотация. Реабилитация – это процесс, направленный на восстановление способности человека функционировать в социальной среде, как технология, она способствует комплексу мероприятий, направленных на реабилитацию на медицинском, бытовом, профессиональном и личностном уровнях. Это вид деятельности, направленный на социальную адаптацию ребенка в обществе, восстановление его социального статуса, восстановление утраченных отношений, и включает в себя комплекс мероприятий, направленных на восстановление способности человека функционировать в социальной среде.

Ключевые слова: Реабилитация, организм, нервная система, пневмония, восстановление, физиотерапия, гипертоническая болезнь, двигательная активность, психическое восстановление.

After the independence of our republic, the attention to the medical field and the preservation of people's health increased even more. For example, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov's decree "For a healthy generation" adopted in 1993, as well as the adoption of many other laws aimed at maintaining the health of the population, achieving physical fitness of the republic's population, and ensuring the inextricable connection between physical and spiritual culture, " The year of healthy generation, the year of patrons and doctors, the year of appreciation of the elderly, the year of mother and child, the year of rural development and well-being, and the year of the perfect generation.

A clear example of this is the modernization of the country, the further improvement of medical and social services, and the implementation of major reforms in the education system.

The positive effect of physical education and sports on the human body has been known in medicine since ancient times.

The great Hakim Abu Ali ibn Sino said, "There is no need to treat a body that is constantly moving." Great attention is paid to the development of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Law "On Physical Education and Sports" adopted on January 14, 1992 stipulates that every member of the community should be engaged in physical education, that children should be involved in it, that they should be well-rounded, strong and healthy in all aspects. It is emphasized that it is important. Currently, special attention is paid to the

development of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Real professional athletes are being trained for the republic in various circles and sections, as well as in sports schools.

The word "rehabilitation" is derived from the Latin language and means "to restore oneself". This term was introduced by ancient doctors and healers, and it means that a doctor should not only help and treat a person in case of illness or injury, but also help his organism to recover its functional activity after illness and injury. For example: let's say a person has a lung disease - pneumonia. On the basis of this disease, the unit of the lung stroma (structure) is damaged, the alveoli are damaged, that is, they become inflamed. Gas exchange takes place in the alveoli. The inflamed alveolus is filled with pus, and the passage of oxygen to the alveolar capillaries becomes difficult or completely destroyed.

As a result, body tissues and CNS (central nervous system) are not adequately supplied with oxygen. This leads to disruption of brain function and cardiovascular system. Pneumonia is treated with antibiotics, expectorants, expectorants, anti-inflammatory drugs, and vitamins. For the functional recovery of the lung organ, rehabilitation procedures last from two weeks to two years (depending on the type of disease, severity level). During this time, special physiotherapeutic procedures - electrophoresis, massage, physical therapy exercises and special breathing exercises should be used.

A patient's recovery, physical and mental recovery after an illness depends more on the care, attention, courtesy and passion of a medical and social worker.

Duties of a medical and social worker in the field of rehabilitation:

- perform all the procedures ordered by the doctor to the patient safely and on time;
- providing general patient care and sanitary-hygienic procedures;
- to be extremely attentive and patient in the care of bedridden patients;
- to be kind and courteous;
- able to explain to the patient why the prescribed procedures are necessary (based on medical knowledge);
- participation in sanitarium-whitening work: to be able to inform the population about the disease and teach its prevention measures, to be able to explain what complications the disease causes;
- being able to provide assistance to patients with serious illnesses in social care departments

There are two main types of medical rehabilitation: general rehabilitation and private rehabilitation. General rehabilitation refers to the strengthening and restoration of the human body's general activity, general condition, and health with the help of procedures that affect all systems. In order to restore the functioning of diseased organs in the patient's body, special treatments are widely used along with natural factors.

Functional rehabilitation means a set of procedures and factors used to restore the function of a body part whose activity is limited or impaired due to complications of an illness or injury. In addition to medical rehabilitation, there are several types of rehabilitation: mental rehabilitation, social rehabilitation, etc. Medical social worker has a great role in medical rehabilitation. In this field, a high level of knowledge, patience, love for the patient, sympathy and responsibility are required from the employee.

Among the diseases, the most common are diseases of the cardiovascular system, including angina pectoris, myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease, congenital and acquired heart diseases (defects), as well as acute and chronic respiratory diseases (bronchitis, asthma, bronchial asthma, lung gangrene and abscess, pulmonary tuberculosis, etc.). In addition, diseases of the digestive system are common.

Among them are acute and chronic gastritis, stomach ulcer disease, colitis and enterocolitis, chronic liver diseases, etc. Patients with these diseases need special, individual and general treatment, as well as rehabilitation measures.

Rehabilitation procedures are determined depending on the type of disease, severity and general condition of the patient. For such patients, treatment complexes, prophylactics and sanatoriums-resorts have been established in the territory of a hospital or polyclinic for the purpose of rehabilitation.

In recent years, therapeutic physical therapy, massage, reflexology and other procedures are widely used for the purpose of rehabilitation after conservative treatment in patients suffering from acute and chronic circulatory failure, hypertension, etc.

Special physical exercises are determined depending on the functional state of the circulatory system. It is always necessary to follow one principle (rule): exercises are gradually increased from simple to complex, and their amplitude from light to active.

Sanatorium treatment is important in the rehabilitation of cardiovascular system diseases. The main task of this method is to widely use the influence of natural factors to restore the activity of diseased members, in particular, members of the YUQTS.

In such a situation, the accurate diagnosis of the patient, the stage of the disease, the degree of its potential are important, as well as determining the effectiveness of the natural healing agent. This method of treatment uses a special routine - active rest, special diet, diet, physical therapy, walks and positive effects of weather, physiotherapeutic procedures.

Physical rehabilitation - restoring or compensating physical ability and mental ability, increasing and improving the functional state of the body, physical education tools and methods, sports elements, sports training, massage, physiotherapy and natural factors to improve the physical ability of the human body, mental and emotional stability and is a system of measures to improve adaptive reserves.

In mental rehabilitation, the main focus is on the correction of the patient's mental state, as well as on the formation of the correct approach to his treatment, doctor's recommendations, and the implementation of rehabilitation measures. In this direction, it is necessary to create the necessary conditions for patients to mentally adapt to life activities that have changed as a result of the disease.

In vocational rehabilitation, the issues of rehabilitation, vocational training and retraining, determination of patients' ability to work are solved or considered.

Socioeconomic rehabilitation focuses on restoring economic independence and social excellence to the injured patient. These tasks should be solved not only by medical institutions, but also by social welfare bodies.

Physiotherapy is a branch of nature that studies the physiological and therapeutic effects of natural and man-made physical factors, develops new methods for the prevention and treatment of disease, as well as therapeutic methods, while in turn applies them to life.

Conclusions and suggestions

In conclusion, rehabilitation methods should be aimed at achieving a high result. Continuous consultation of patients helps in its implementation. Social rehabilitation allows them to adapt to changing family and social life conditions. They are activities aimed at improving the quality of life, creating equal opportunities for full participation in society. Thus, we must understand that psychological recovery of a person plays an important role along with medical treatment. Don't ignore it.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmedov A., Sodikova Z. Normal anatomy and physiology. T., 2000.
2. Ganiyev S. V. Fundamentals of traumatology and orthopedics.
3. Ilkhoyayeva K.E., Khudoyberganova B.T. Physiotherapy and medical rehabilitation. T., 2004.
4. Muradov N.N. Healing spaces of the trade union of Uzbekistan. T., 1995.
5. Studenkin M.Ya. Directory of pediatricians.
6. Haydarov S.O. Internal diseases.
7. Yuldashev K.E. Physiotherapy. T., 1990
8. EVERAOH.COM